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TIN 492-741-614
lakbaydiwapublishing@gmail.com
Butuan City, Philippines
+639543906965

Archie T. Ramirez, PhD CJ

Associate Professor 3

Biliran Province State University

Biliran Province, Eastern Visayas

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Crystals and Shadows: A Life Smoked in Silence

In a dark, side-lined night, negotiations are uttered
Loaded with packs, and white crystals are shared
Armed with guns and bullets, secretly full of hatred
At any point in time, he is prepared for war if needed

Confidently confined, clear smoke, death begins
Moving faster than light, surrounded by rotted brains
Escaping better dreams, triggering the future left hanging
Ending the lives of loved ones is perfectly convincing

A home of paradise, a world of heaven alike
Filled with blood, covered with voices, and contains a spike
Peace and order have once been promised,
Developing the place into a fearless battlefield

Once tasted, it's hard to let go, as they say
Poison runs in the blood, and addiction will be
But time is unending, only for a heart so desired
Changing lives is still possible with God, so admired

It's not only about the act of a felony, but also the suffering of a family
A scar that lives forever, a bleeding heart felt endlessly
Rebuilding relationships is a top priority,
Leading the way to a life with grace abundantly

When the day comes, he is armed to fight
He is focused and dedicated to bringing back the light
Defeating future thieves is the answer to breaking the curse
Positioning the justice, it deserves to tighten the loose